

Obstacles to Effective Policing in Nigeria

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Abstract: This paper aims to investigate Nigeria's challenges to efficient policing. Reviewing books, journals, and online papers served as a secondary means of data collection. Utilizing content analysis, the extracted data was examined. Based on the examined literature, the report identified a number of causes for Nigeria's apparent high crime rate, including widespread unemployment, extreme poverty, and political intolerance. The police have developed techniques including surveillance, information gathering, undercover operations, stop, search, and detention, among others, to reduce crime and criminal behaviour in response to what appears to be a high prevalence of crime in Nigeria. These tactics were nevertheless found to be not very effective, and this was attributed to the numerous difficulties the Nigerian security system faces, including the general lack of cooperation on the part of the populace, inadequate crime prevention and control tools, poor pay, corruption, a lack of manpower, and inadequate funding, among others. As a result of the foregoing, it was suggested that the government focus its efforts on addressing the root causes of crime, i.e., removing the factors that encourage crime as a worthwhile option to following the law. Police officers should be trained and retrained because they also require higher pay.

Keywords: Obstacles, Effectiveness, Policing, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to ensure the safety of community members and conformance to societal norms and values, policing as a concept refers to the measures and actions taken by a range of institutions and groups to regulate social relations and behaviour (Reiner, 2000:3). So, it is a subset of control procedures that includes making a monitoring system and threatening to punish people who don't follow the rules.

For example, in Nigeria, policing must take into account the actions of the Nigeria Police Force, the military, at least eight paramilitary units, several palace guards, a large number of quasi-official units in different states, and various thugs who work for strongmen (Heap, 2000; Ismail, 2008).

It has become vital to explore for causative explanations that go beyond simple semantics in the light of the continuously occurring acts of lawlessness, social disorder, armed robbery, and pointless vindictive assassination, among others (Achebe, 1959). One of the biggest issues Nigeria is now dealing with is crime. This is shown by the fact that the national dailies always have news about some kind of crime, such as murder, forced rape, aggravated assault, kidnapping, gang violence, gunmen, and suicide bombers, whose recent killings have left many homes crying and gnashing their teeth (Okunola, 2002:32).

The seeming lack of security of life and property in Nigeria has prevented both domestic and foreign investors from seriously considering making large-scale investments across the whole nation. Without a doubt, this situation represents a warning sign for the progress of the country.

Modern technical growth and enormous communication advances have made it easier for criminal operations to be committed, utilizing sophisticated equipment in one location while escaping to another location, making crime as complex

as human nature (Onyeozili, 2008). According to Onyeozili (2008), the globe today faces a number of grave issues, including terrorism, hijacking, kidnapping, and the trafficking of illegal drugs.

It is regrettable to see that crime is quickly expanding in many forms despite the strong national and international effort to combat such crime. Crime has had a negative impact on both developing and developed countries by degrading the quality of life, endangering fundamental freedoms and human rights, and constituting a major threat to the community. Even though the problem may be different in each country in terms of how bad it is and how big it is, no country is still affected by it.

A crime is an omission that is subject to legal repercussions. A crime committed in one location at one time might not be committed in another. Crime is primarily caused by two things: opportunity and malicious intent. Even though someone has the intention of committing a crime, they cannot do so until and unless they are given the chance. So, the best way to stop crime is to take away all of the chances for it to happen, whether through traditional or community policing (Igbaji, 2013).

Police, courts, corrections personnel, and others who work in the criminal justice system and allied institutions like the mental health and juvenile justice systems were used in previous government efforts to reduce crime in Nigeria (Okunola, 2002; Kornblum and Julian, 2004; Alemika, 1997; Dambazau, 1994; Hale, 2004).

In light of this, the goal of this research is to find out what makes it hard for police in Nigeria to do their jobs well.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

According to current events in the world, particularly in Nigeria, crime and criminal activity seem to be a permanent part of our contemporary society (Chijoke, 2007). A fundamental right guaranteed by Nigeria's 1999 constitution's Chapter II Section 14 Subsection 2(b) is the security of life and property. Successful regimes have worked to implement this fundamental right, particularly since 1999. However, rising poverty, wide income gaps, high unemployment, social dislocation brought on by widespread rural-urban migration and the deterioration of social values, which led to business fraud (419, drug abuse, etc.), as well as neighbourhood unrest, account for growing concerns about the country's level of insecurity and unrest.

Even though the police, law enforcement agencies, the army, community leaders, vigilantes, and some angry members of the public are all working together to deal with the current security problems and stop or at least slow down the rise of crime, it seems like their efforts are going to waste because criminal behaviour is so dynamic and complicated.

Since new criminal strategies are developed every day in our culture, the rate of crime is rising and hasn't yet been reduced.

Given the foregoing, it is fair to say that there is some quiet over how Nigerian police should be done effectively. In order to better understand these challenges, this paper will look at Nigeria.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This paper's overarching goal is to pinpoint Nigeria's policing challenges.

The following are some of the explicit goals of this essay:

- i. To investigate the causes of Nigeria's allegedly high crime rate.
- ii. To investigate the methods used by Nigerian police to combat crime.
- iii. To list the main tactics for efficient crime prevention.

4. METHODOLOGY

For this work, secondary sources or a method of data gathering were used. The paper's goals were used to review and analyse the content of books, journals, and online articles, among other things.

5. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The review of pertinent and related literature with a theoretical focus is the focus of this paper. As a result, it will include analyzing a wide range of sources relevant to the research topic, such as books, reports, publications, academic journal articles, archive materials, and internet-based recorded source materials. So, based on the goals of this paper, the review of relevant and related literature will be broken down into the following subheadings:

5.1 The Police and Policing Concept

It's critical to distinguish between the concepts of "police" and "policing" in this context. By doing this, "police" refers to a certain type of social institution, whereas "policing" denotes a collection of procedures with distinct social roles, according to Alemika (2003). Police organizations and personnel can take on a variety of different shapes, and the police are not present in every civilization. However, it might be argued that "policing," which can be accomplished through a variety of different procedures and institutional frameworks, is a must in every social order. According to Ehindero (1993), the police were founded by the state to uphold order and enforce the law. As a result, just like the state, the nation's political and economic structures shape the nature, functions, and priorities of the police force.

Similar to how policing by state and non-state agencies takes many forms, it also depends on the nature and make-up of the social political economy (Ehindero, 1993). The duties of the police are determined by the tensions and conflicts of interests among social classes and organizations, which, if unchecked, can endanger the maintenance of the status quo. The police serve as a direct reflection of societal tensions, disputes, and human collaboration (Alemika, 2003).

Using the political economy framework can help any society understand the police and how they do their jobs.

5.2 A brief overview of policing in Nigeria, Africa, and the rest of the world

Individual residents were mostly in charge of upholding law and order throughout the early days of policing (Reiner, 2000). Constables and justices of the peace traditionally worked without compensation and served in their positions voluntarily. To manage law enforcement operations in their shires in England and their nations in the colonies, shire reeves, or sheriffs, were employed full-time. This makeshift way of keeping people in line worked very well for a long time, especially in rural and sparsely populated areas (Adler, 2001).

However, major American and English cities experienced a population increase in the late 1700s and early 1800s, according to Adler (2001). Riots and other kinds of civil unrest happened often, and it became clear that the country needed a stronger, more capable police force that had the official backing of the government.

A centralized police force was advocated for by philosophers, sociologists, and experts in the newly emerging discipline of criminology, particularly legal philosophers, in order to safeguard the populace and preserve order. Sir Robert Peel, a member of parliament and Home Secretary for the United Kingdom in the 1820s, was possibly the most influential proponent of a professional police force (Adler, 2001). Peel founded the London Metropolitan police department in 1829. With the creation of the London police force, Peel became known among historians and criminologists as the founder of modern policing (Adler, 2001).

Policing in Africa is less clearly defined in practice than it is in Western nations, and its definition likely has to be expanded beyond the actions of formal organizations (Reiner, 2000). For instance, in Nigeria, policing must be viewed in light of the actions of the Nigeria Police Force, the military, at least eight paramilitary units, several palace guards, multiple quasi-official units in various states, and various thugs connected to strongmen. Numerous organizations, including the Bakassi Boys and the Odua Peoples Congress (OPC), which operate under the patronage of some state governors, engage in vigilante policing (Heap, 2000; Ismail, 2008).

5.3 The Global Characteristics of Modern Policing

Modern law enforcement is an extremely intricate process that cannot be done in a vacuum. It is being shaped by a number of factors and individuals, and the communities and cultures in which it is occurring are also being shaped by it (Reiner, 2000). The practice of policing is clearly shifting from "policing for the state" to "policing for the community" on a global scale. However, policing necessitates a shift in organization as well as philosophy and technique. The police also need to collaborate with other police groups in the neighbouring nations and around the world as crime becomes more and more transnational (Glueck & Glueck, 1951).

For the police, all of these changes pose fresh difficulties. The police need a lot of knowledge and expertise to effectively handle all of these obstacles and demands. They also need to share experience and collaborate closely with other law enforcement organizations, both domestically and internationally. As a result, it can be claimed that modern policing is supported by four pillars, each of which must be solid and equally strong for policing to be successful in carrying out its mandate globally. Cooperation, training, education, and research make up these four pillars (Glueck & Glueck, 1951).

5.4 Nigeria's Policing Structure

In accordance with Odekunle (2005), understanding the nature of policing around the globe, particularly in Africa and Nigeria, offers a laboratory for us to consider the potential role policing may play in Security Sector Reforms (SSRs) and also exemplifies some of the ways the police interact with other actors in the security sector. Putting police reform in post-colonial states in historical perspective is helpful. We have the chance to pinpoint the elements systematically impeding or impeding fundamental change in policing because of its duration (many of which apply to transitional states in other regions). It is evident from a study of police reform in the post-colonial states of sub-Saharan Africa that African police forces develop through political adaptation and accommodating regimes rather than through a linear progression towards a Western model of apprehending criminals and being held accountable to the public (Odekunle, 2005). Therefore, more than any aid program, historical inheritance, socio-political forces, individual ambition, political contingencies, and institutional resilience have significantly impacted them. Based on this evidence, Hills (2001) said that security sector reform programs have not yet dealt with the kind of political power that makes it hard for the police to do their jobs.

Without a doubt, Nigeria has been dealing with what is known as a "crime-problem" in criminological literature since the middle of the 1970s (Odekunle, 2005). It is appropriate to refer to a situation as a social problem when crime moves from a normal or tolerated level of incidence and severity to the pathological stage and calls for several actions from the police, the community, and the government. Odekunle (2005) asserts that crime prevention is a risky and time-consuming endeavour. The police must not just be knowledgeable, courageous, and diligent in their work. Numerous duties and tasks are involved in being a police officer. Officers are supposed to prevent crime, safeguard people and property, uphold the law, preserve public order, and offer a variety of services to the public. The likelihood of violence and the necessity and legitimacy of using coercive measures to impose social control, however, are a common theme tying these disparate activities together (Bitner, 1970). The organization is responsible for providing the resources needed for a police officer to carry out his or her duties.

5.5 Obstacles to Effective Policing in Nigeria

Apart from material seen in daily newspapers, there is ample official and scientific support for this claim. Therefore, it is unnecessary to "prove" the Nigeria Police Force's subpar performance in the current contribution. Instead, what is required is the identification of the primary deficiencies, issues, and challenges that are to blame for the state of affairs (Yebo, 2004). In Nigeria, a number of things have been cited as obstacles or barriers to efficient policing. Among these things are the following, which are emphasized and critically discussed:

(i) Insufficient financing

The main barriers that have historically prevented spending on preventing crime from being channelled into building up criminal justice systems are a lack of money and inadequate funding (Adewusi, 1990). The United Nations Department of Public Information says that more money is needed for future research, even though spending on community and situation prevention has gone up over the past 20 years and topics like child development are starting to get more attention (UNDPI, 2000).

To adapt crime control and preventive strategies to increasingly modern crimes, such as organized and multinational crimes, funding will be required (Adewusi, 1990). As trade and commerce become more global, business and leisure travel expand, and traditional borders open up, the current levels of these offenses could skyrocket (UNDPI, 2000).

According to Odekunle (2004), crime investigation and detection require a lot of resources. Money is needed to hire, train, equip, and mobilize a suitable number of criminal investigators. According to Elgege (2006), when a crime is reported to the police in Nigeria, the custom is for the complaint desk officer to ask for money to buy stationery so they can file the complaint. Once the necessity to visit the crime scene arises, the complainant will be required to provide transportation since the criminal investigations department typically does not have a vehicle. The complainant or the accused is required to pay for a post-mortem examination if the offense involves a murder, because funding is not available for such procedures. When an investigation is over, the complainant or the defendant is also required to pay for the duplicate of the case file for the investigation. The aforementioned makes it abundantly evident that criminal investigations in Nigeria are underfunded. According to Otuba and Coker, this underfunding is a result of both the overall underfunding of the Nigerian Police as a whole and internal corruption (2006:67).

(ii) The Nigerian Police's type of training and qualifications

As a result of the nature of their training, many police officers spend much of their time performing monotonous, everyday tasks like filling out paperwork and waiting for something to happen, rather than dealing with crisis situations or firing weapons while performing their duties (Tappan, 1960). The Nigerian police force is unable to reduce crime rates due to a lack of experienced and trained personnel (Swimer, 1974). According to Alemika (1999), many police departments failed to emphasize during recruitment the qualities necessary for policing, such as a high level of intelligence, education, tact, sound judgment, physical courage, emotional stability, impartiality, and honesty, which are typically lacking in police officers during their time on duty due to insufficient education during training and recruitment. A 1995 study that compared 1993 to 1990 in United States statistics indicated that twice as many police agencies needed officers to have some college education, with 8% requiring some kind of degree and 1% requiring a four-year degree, demonstrating the growing emphasis on the necessity for police education (Alemika, 1999).

The Nigeria Police's criminal investigations are conducted by officers of lower ranks than sergeants. The majority of these constable investigators have just completed the basic three-month entry-level training at the Police College, where the majority of their education has been focused on physical training with little time given to the art of policing. While still a novice, the officer is assigned to conduct complex investigations since she lacks the expertise and training necessary for real criminal investigation (Alemika, 1999). In his first press conference after taking office on January 15, 2005, the former Inspector General of Police, Mr. Sunday Ehindero, who is quoted in Otubu and Coker (2006:38), confirmed this position. He said that:

The time when novices were sent to look into criminal offenses is over. Instead of sending a tailor to look into something, we need to take a census of all individuals with professional understanding, such as accountants. No one will automatically be posted to the CID (Criminal Investigations Department) unless they have something to offer, and we will make use of them.

Sadly, the endorsements on the investigation reports show that this problem still exists (Otubu & Coker, 2006:38).

According to Alemika (1997), Osaba (1994), and Balogun (2003), these deficiencies are crucial in terms of manpower, both in terms of quantity and quality. That is, the effectiveness of the force is impacted by the quality of the police force, some of whom have poor communication skills. Additionally, they assert that the performance of the police force is impacted by poor criminal and operational information management practices, including erroneous recording and compiling of information, insufficient analysis, and infrequent dissemination of statistics.

(iii) Lack of adequate Personnel in the Nigerian Police Force

It is well known that the Nigerian police force consistently lacks manpower in a number of important sectors. For instance, the force had 143,204 members altogether in 1993. (Annual Report of the NPF, 1993:3). The Nigerian police population ratio was 1:618 in 1991, based on the nation's 83.5 million inhabitants. The United Nations recommends one police officer for every 400 people, which falls short of this. One police officer for every 400 people is now the norm in many western nations (including the United States, Britain, France, and others), which is thought to be reasonable for improving crime control (Clinard and Abott, 1973:219).

It is undisputed, according to Okereke (1995), that the Nigerian police force is understaffed. The workers at different police stations are so overworked that concerns are frequently politely rejected by citing a lack of staff as a handy excuse for the inability to respond promptly or effectively. Not only does the Nigerian police force lack personnel, but it also lacks qualified personnel.

(iv) Lack of Appropriate Equipment

In order to effectively combat crime, Philip (1999) contends that walkie-talkies, radios, and telephones are essential tools. Radios and walkie-talkies are typically broken or even unusable where they are present. According to Philip (1999), the Nigerian police force is in need of more vehicles, especially quick-moving, reliable patrol cars. As a result, they rarely pursue criminals in hot pursuit.

Roebuck (2000) asserts that it is a well-known fact that dangerous criminals, such as armed robbers, have significantly better weapons than the police. While the majority of armed robbers typically carry high-tech automatic guns, There aren't many armed police officers. Their most popular weapons are the short rifle and the Mark IV rifle, both of which are difficult to carry and wield. Most police officers carry truncheons and batons, which don't work against criminals or other troublemakers (Membere, 1999).

According to Membere (1999), the police need to be equipped with advanced weapons so they can hold their own against criminals like armed robbers who frequently use advanced weapons. But the cops should only ever employ these weapons as a last option. A major reason why cops have failed is the inadequate state of their arsenal (Membere, 1999). According to Dauda (2008), Nigerian police are useless when confronted with armed thieves because these youngsters have sophisticated machines that the authorities cannot dare to withstand.

(v) Unethical behaviour

Corruption is one of the major issues preventing socioeconomic progress in the Nigerian police (Garoupa, 2002). As wealthy and influential Nigerians compete with one another in the theft of the so-called "National Cake," corruption is pervasive and has practically become institutionalized (Garoupa, 2002). According to Bonger (1990), the police are not immune from corruption, because they are an integral component of Nigerian society. Ahire (1991) asserts that extortion of meagre sums of money, or what one may refer to as "peanut money," from operators of commercial vehicles and traffic infractions is a prevalent kind of police corruption. Our main worry is not this. Our main worry is that police corruption, no matter how much of it there is, encourages and facilitates rather than deters criminal activity in our nation (Ahire, 1991).

The Nigeria Police Force has a large-scale corruption and extortion problem. The reputation of the police has been severely tarnished by this behaviour. (Neild, 2004). Asserting that police corruption is a severe problem because they are expected to be morally honest as law enforcement officers, Alemika (1999:10) agrees with Neild. The safety of society is in jeopardy if the police, who are charged with preventing, detecting, and prosecuting crime and corruption, are also corrupt. The police also possess authority that has a significant impact on residents' lives, property, and safety. Citizens feel unsafe where such power is tainted by corrupt tendencies. Extortion, a type of robbery, is another manifestation of this corruption. (Neild, 2004). According to Uruena (2003), police corruption explains why such activities endanger the public and why the police are therefore unable to live up to expectations. Alemika (1999) asserts that police brutality is frequently used as a tactic for pressuring people to give in to demands for bribes and that it occasionally serves as a form of punishment for refusing to comply with the police's demands for satisfaction. The Nigeria Police is not exempt from the corruption that permeates Nigeria's political system, claims Neild (2004). In Nigeria, one of the most obvious examples of corruption is police corruption. The typical Nigerian is accustomed to seeing police officials levying a "toll" at checkpoints set up all around the nation. The police are crooked, and it affects criminal investigations in addition to the roadblocks. According to Neild (2004), a large number of crimes go unsolved by the police when powerful people, such as members of the government, are named as suspects or when the suspects "sort the police detectives," which is slang for paying bribes. Despite the creation of the "X Squad Section" in 1963, corruption still exists within the Nigerian Police. One of the sections within the Nigeria Police Force's Force Criminal Investigations Department is the X Squad Section, and its duties include looking into and rooting out corruption among the force's officers. Even though the X Squad Section is still listed on the Nigeria Police Force's organogram, it seems that it is no longer in use (Uruena, 2003).

(vi) The general lack of cooperation

The Nigerian police force used the catchphrase "the cops are your friends" in one of its public relations jingles. Another amusing one advises calling in a "thug" the next time you are in trouble if the police are not your pals. A bold illustration of a thug with clean-cut hair wearing dark sunglasses, a heavy club or iron bar, and smoking what appears to be pot or marijuana is placed on top of this cynical counsel (The Guardian, June 14th, 2000. Lagos). According to Adewusi (1990), the majority of the populace views police officers with contempt, mistrust, and suspicion. They view them as enemies on the side of criminals rather than as friends and allies in the fight against crime. Because of this, they are afraid to help or work with the police in any way.

Igbo (1992) asserts that a lack of confidence in the Nigerian police frequently results in a decision not to cooperate with them and occasionally in the lurching of suspects by enraged mobs. A good example is the mass lurching of known offenders in Onitsha and its surroundings on June 28, 1979, carried out by members of the Onitsha Amalgamated Traders Association (OATA). The widespread protest came when local Onitsha thieves, robbers, con artists, and dupes repeatedly harassed the traders. Instead of allowing the "due process" of the law to be followed in dealing with criminals, members of OATA were forced to resort to "jungle justice." This was essentially a vote of confidence in the police or charges against them in the eyes of Igbo (1992). Another recent instance is how the "area guys" delivered swift punishment to known and suspected armed robbers in Lagos Island on June 6 and 7, 1999. The house-to-house sweep operation that resulted in the capture of at least 19 alleged armed robbers, who were then burned alive in various locations around Lagos Island (Tempo, June 24th, 2007). 1999, vol. 12, ND.24.p.7)

According to Westley (1953), criminal investigation is not a black art but rather principally depends on information provided to the investigator in the form of a witness' report or a victim's complaint. Over the years, the Nigerian Police have voiced complaints about the unwillingness of the Nigerian people to file complaints and report crimes and criminal activity.

The Nigerian public's reluctance to provide information to the Nigerian police is not without justification, and this situation has even been brought up in court a number of times (Westley, 1953). Ismail (2008) asserts that since the repressive era of the Hausa Constabulary Guards, formed in 1861 by the British colonial authorities, the average Nigerian has had awe for the police. The Hausa Constabulary, which preceded the current Nigeria Police, was only responsible for employing force against the native population to defend British colonial interests. As a result of the potential police information leak to the suspects, there is currently a constant dread of being implicated in committing the crime one reports to the police and of being attacked in retaliation by the person the report is filed against (Okereke, 1993). Also, it's not uncommon for the police to ask the person who reports a crime to pay for the investigation and make several trips back to the station for different reasons, which wastes a lot of time (Ismail, 2008).

(vii) Language barriers

Language barriers are just additional barrier to efficient police in Nigeria, claims Kunle (2005). People use their "mother tongue" for daily socialization in a pluralistic, semi-illiterate culture. A "foreigner" or "outsider" (someone who is not a native speaker of the given language) finds it challenging to interact effectively with the natives in such a society. This is the case in Nigeria, where a Hausa-speaking police officer in the country's multilingual police force would find it hard to do his job of preventing social unrest in a Yoruba or Igbo-speaking area (Kunle, 2005). Ohonbamu (1972) says that (mis)communication was still a problem even after the colonial police realized they had made a mistake and put more emphasis on practical language skills than academic ones in order to improve the roles of police in civil society.

(viii) Constitutional issue

Another barrier to successful policing in Nigeria, as seen in the Second Republic, is constitutional issues. Between 1987 and 1983, disagreements arose about whether a federal organization with a unified or decentralized army would be better able to maintain law and order in the country (Report of the Political Bureau, 1987; 104). All evidence points to Nigeria's current policy of overly consolidating police power in the hands of the executive president, who has employed the police to silence any opposing voices. (Odekunle, 1979) The police have often taken sides with certain groups and worked with them based on who stands to gain.

The involvement of the police in state political governance during the military regimes of 1966–1975 and 1984–1999, respectively, is closely tied to this. According to Tamuno and Takena (1970), military juntas appointed some of these police officials as state governors, putting them in positions of political power. Their goal changed from keeping the peace in a civil society to undermining the integrity of the department so they wouldn't get good political jobs. This made it much harder for them to be fair (Tamuno and Takena, 1970).

Former minister of police affairs, David Jemibewon, examined the issues facing the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) and concluded that the "Nigerian factor" is to blame for the poor performance of the Nigerian police. These factors, along with others, are covered by this phenomenon. He used the illustration that when a man is arrested by the police in Nigeria, an Alhaji, a Reverend, or a leader will call before you know it. The criminal will grovel on the street, or the wealthy one will buy his way through. (The Guardian, 2000, June 20). Favouritism toward family members or friends through preferential hiring and advancement is referred to as nepotism and ethnicity. In Nigeria, it is well known that some parts of the country have more people in the military and police at the highest levels, and this is often reflected in promotions (Odekunle, 2004).

Odekunle says that protégés are put in charge of police departments even though they are not qualified to do so.

Inadequacy of both qualitative and quantitative manpower; excessive station workload; a lack of equipment; indolence, negligence, and corruption; undue delay of cases referred for the direct or of public prosecution advice; outdated methods of recruitment; and subpar training performance are just a few of the issues that police commissioner Danmadani (1999; 166-117) listed as impeding the effective performance of their duties.

(ix) A moral character deficit

Elgege (2006) asserts that a public official's integrity is a vital value. It directs how one behaves while performing official duties. For instance, the Nigerian Police Force lacks integrity. The officers frequently display their lack of professionalism and extreme unreliability by taking part in criminal activity or collaborating with offenders. They frequently defend the

wealthy in their daily work. Through bribery, blackmail, and intimidation, they frequently use their status to oppress their fellow citizens. This was also expressed by Dauda (2008): "The police, in my opinion, are a shame to Nigerians; they conduct awful things... Consider the scenario where police kill an innocent person and then claim the next day that he was caught stealing.

(x) Police brutality and harassment of helpless citizens

These are additional significant barriers that stand in the Nigeria Police's way of ensuring the safety of people and their property as well as the maintenance of law and order. Ismail (2008) asserts that the police frequently broke the law with the support of autocratic leaders and oppressive laws. Most of the time, police have acted as if they were the law, killing innocent people and arbitrarily detaining people without consequence. Political opponents of governments, workers, radicalized students, and human rights activists have always been subjected to disproportionately high rates of police brutality, kidnappings, unlawful searches and seizures, invasions of privacy, extrajudicial killings, bodily harm, intimidation, and harassment, as well as loss of personal freedoms (Alemika, 1993b:208).

According to Dauda (2008), after an elected government took office on May 29, 1999, police repression (especially extrajudicial killings) did not stop. According to a press release issued by the Force Police Public Relations Officer in early January 2001, armed robbers killed 134 people between August 15 and December 19, 2000, while injuring 320 more. Of the 134 victims, 88 were police officers, while 29 more were killed. But in the same time frame, 348 robbery suspects were slain by the police. A Nigerian police publication says that there were about 10,345 reports of armed robberies in the country between 1996 and 2000, and that 13,365 people were arrested during that time.

In comparison to the 381 policemen slain by thieves and the 822 policemen injured during the study period, 2,201 armed hoodlums died in gun battles with the police.

(xi) Inadequacies in resources and management

These have also affected the effectiveness and behaviour of the police. In conclusion, the following are some of the Nigerian police force's critical shortcomings, according to Alemika (1997), 1998, Osoba, 1994, and Balogun (2003):

1. A lack of manpower, particularly in terms of quality rather than quantity.
2. Inadequate management of criminal and operational information, including inaccurate recording, collation, storage, and retrieval; insufficient analysis; and infrequent release of criminal statistics
3. Low commitment due to low pay and working conditions.
4. A lack of proper liberal and comprehensive training that can shed light on the nature and sources of law and crime, as well as inadequate initial and on-the-job training, are all contributing factors.
5. Improper resource allocation
6. Inadequate transportation, telecommunication, logistics, weapons and ammunition, uniforms and accoutrements, and facilities-both in terms of quantity and quality.
7. Inadequate residential and office space
8. Suspects are abused while being held in police cells.
9. An unsanitary work environment
11. Limited interactions or relationships with the general public outside of their roles in law enforcement and peacekeeping.
13. Discipline issues, criminal activity, or cooperation with offenders.
14. abusing the justice system (i.e., obtaining and supplying false evidence, tampering with exhibits, and false accusations combined with a lack of legal knowledge and disregard for human rights).

5.6 Factors Responsible for the Seemingly High Rates of Crime in Nigeria

Scholars have worked hard to pinpoint the causes of Nigeria's allegedly rising crime rate, including Adedokun (1990), Egwu (1990), Odekunle (2005), Akinrinde (2007), Arinze (2010), Ajibade, Olopade and Erinsho (2011), and others. For example, Adedokun and Egwu (1990) linked the issue to the crisis of global capitalism and its boom-bust cycle. These

academics say that the Nigerian government's response to the crisis has been austerity, high unemployment, and food shortages, all of which have made the country's crime problem worse.

According to Odekunle (2005), the rise in the crime rate is primarily caused by relative poverty and unemployment. Akinrinde (2007) linked the issue of declining income and low savings to the rising crime rate. Many laid-off workers reportedly found themselves fighting for survival because they had no source of income and no savings to fall back on. Many people who are unable to find other employment but must maintain their physical and mental well-being choose to turn to crime. In his own submission, Arinze (2010) emphasized the importance of unemployment and a high rate of inflation that reduced real income as the causes of Nigeria's ostensibly high crime rate. Scholars like Erinsho et al identified the ruling party's intolerance as a factor in Kogi state, along with mass unemployment and a high rate of poverty (2011). According to Odekunle (2005), there are a number of economic and socio-demographic factors that affect people's minds and behaviours and that contribute to Nigeria's high rate of crime, including poverty, social exclusion, income inequality, cultural and family background, religion, unemployment, education, age, gender, race, and urbanization. Therefore, according to Ekpenyoung (1999:25), neither economic structures nor leadership philosophies are exclusive to criminal activity. Additionally, the rate of economic development and growth has no special bearing on crime. However, this does not imply that criminal activity is uniform or similar worldwide.

According to Egwu (1999), there are "weaks" and "strongs" in Nigerian society, including the physically, socially, politically, and economically weak and vice versa. Human nature dictates that one group will seek to exploit the other in order to survive and grow. As a result, there are social ills everywhere, including crimes like thuggery, armed robbery, arson, murder, rape, butlery, assault, and other different kinds of crimes.

5.7 Methods for preventing crime by Nigeria Police Force

The Nigerian police have used each of the following mechanisms to carry out their duties in crime prevention:

(a) Beat Patrols

The area that a specific constable or team of constables is assigned to patrol during a single shift is known as a beat. Depending on the population density, the known crime rate, and the economic or administrative significance of the enterprise or building in the region, a precinct in a city or town may be as small as a few streets or roads or as vast as a kilometer radius (Ismail & Abiodun, 2007). These researchers claim that in rural areas, it might be a cluster of villages or hamlets or a kilometer-long section of our national borders. The relevant police officer may travel on foot, bicycles, horses, or cars, and, when necessary, with the help of police-trained dogs, depending on the size, character, and extent of the beat to be covered (this has become rare and non-existent after independence). The main goal of the beat patrol system is to distribute police officers so that there is less chance for misconduct and more chance that a criminal will be caught either as they are committing an offense or right away after. Without a doubt, the high chance of instant capture serves as a powerful deterrent to potential criminals (Ismail & Abiodun, 2007:76).

According to this, the majority of crimes would have been prevented, saving money on legal fees and avoiding the need for incarceration. The ineffective practice of assigning Divisional Police Officers (DPO) to localities in the 1970s and 1980s was a knock-on effect of the beat system. Otubu & Coker (2000) praised the policy and pointed to the Nigerian factor in the body polity as the cause of its demise in light of the circumstances. The law would have greatly assisted the police in their efforts to prevent crime and would have helped to halt the spread of official corruption within the organization. It might be argued that a police officer who works in his or her community is more likely to be familiar with the area's trouble spots and most likely the criminals and potential criminals who reside there. Since it's easy for people to find out where he comes from and judge him because of it, he won't take bribes from locals out of fear of being judged.

Even though this system is good and good for the long run, it won't work well in a culture that values mistrust, racism, favouritism, and corruption (Otubu & Coker, 2000).

Otubu & Coker (2000) assert that the country's institutional and logistical support must come from both the public and private sectors if the system is to succeed. The system may malfunction in areas without a support system, such as good roads, a dependable communication system, or an effective energy backup, because it depends so heavily on prompt, efficient, and effective communication networks. Additionally, the system's initial capital expenditure for national implementation may be absurd. Even so, one could also agree that crime detection and prevention have gotten better since the country started using GSM phones (Otubu and Coker, 2000).

(b) Anti-violence squads

This is a covert surveillance unit that keeps watch over locations that could serve as hotbeds for various vices like prostitution, gambling, and rioting, among other vices. They operate in areas where there is a high rate of theft and fighting, such as large gatherings, public areas, car parks, etc. (Otubu & Coker, 2006:45). The squad's goal is to gather information, offer proactive measures to stop crime from happening, and, if those don't work, at least quickly apprehend offenders at the scene of the crime. The police authorities have used this tactic to conduct raids on these hotbeds of crime at various points, with varying degrees of success. These raids have occasionally resulted in the arrest and prosecution of drug users, dealers in illegal weapons, robbers, and others. According to Balogun (2002), the effectiveness of the system as a tool for preventing crime is questioned. In addition to being expensive to maintain over time, it also portrays the police in a negative light because it suggests a fire brigade approach to managing and preventing crime. A zealous police officer could also easily abuse the system.

(c) Stop, Question, and Arrest

A police officer on duty has the authority to stop, detain, and search anyone who he reasonably suspects is in possession of something that he has reason to believe was stolen, obtained illegally, or in connection with which an offense has been committed. This is done thanks to the authority granted by Section 25 of the Police Act. Police officers are also expected to be vigilant. (Balogun, 2002) When this method is used carefully by police, it does a great job of both finding crimes and stopping them from happening.

(d) Escorts for money

Armed police officers guard large amounts of money, valuables, or explosives while they are being moved. This service is free for government and quasi-government institutions, but private businesses and individuals have to pay for it (Otubu & Coker, 2006).

(e) Static guards

During the colonial era and the first republic, this significant anti-crime prevention approach was adopted throughout the advanced world and partially in Nigeria. In accordance with this concept, police officers are posted at public buildings and locations to monitor the entry and exit of patrons and clients, among other activities, and to deter crimes involving those locations. It is true that the advancement of closed-circuit television has eclipsed this crime prevention strategy, but governmental institutions and installations continue to employ it. Many attempts to damage oil pipelines in the Niger delta region have been successful (Ikelegbe, 2005; Ahmed, 2006; Ikporupo, 2007). Recently, guards at NNPC installations were given guns (Ikelegbe, 2005; Ahmed, 2006; Ikporupo, 2007).

(f) National and internal security

In order to prevent sabotage and subversion of the country and its established institutions, the police, in coordination with the pertinent state security organizations, also provide a surveillance network on the activities of people considered security concerns. However, internal security has been criticized over the years due to the tragic number of fatalities of unidentified people, many of which remain unresolved to this day due to the sluggish investigation procedures carried out by the Nigerian police (Odekunle, 2004). The murders of Chief Bola Ige, a former justice minister, in December 2001 in Ibadan; Barrister and Mrs. Igwe in September 2002 in Onitsha; Alhaji Isiaku Muhammed in September 2002 in Kano; Sir Theodore Agwatu in February 2003 in Owerri; Chief Ogbonna Uche also in February 2003; and Dr. Harry Mashall in March 2003, among other attempted murders and thefts, are notable murder cases that have not been solved (Neild, 2004). Such circumstances have raised issues about the Nigerian police and policing tactics, particularly in connection to intelligence-information collection since independence. These are attributable to the negative public perception of the police, which has also discouraged people from providing the police with important information (Olujinmi, 2004; Bruce & Neild, 2004). However, without the support of the general population, the tasks of crime prevention, detection, and conviction cannot be properly carried out. In this context, Odekunle (2004:56) emphasized the difficulties facing law enforcement under four key criteria:

1. Effectiveness (a lower or lower rate of criminal victimization; a higher percentage of crimes known to the police being cleared by arrest; a greater amount of stolen property recovered; a higher percentage of arrests ending in conviction; a lower rate of traffic accidents; and a faster response time to reports/complaints).

2. Receptivity (higher citizen perception of crime safety; higher citizen ratings of overall police performance; higher citizen ratings of specific police activities; and higher citizen ratings of specific aspects of police behaviour such as honesty, integrity, courtesy, and fairness).
3. Equity (with reference to the egalitarian distribution of "protection" to all sections of the population).
4. Effectiveness (with reference to cost-and-benefit analysis of "protection" output relative to monetary, human, and material input).

There is no question that policing in Nigeria is not where it was after independence, based on the aforementioned definitions and measures of successful policing. Most Nigerians know that the Nigeria Police Force doesn't do as well as it could base on the listed criteria, especially when it comes to gathering information and intelligence (Odekunle, 2004).

5.8 Major Strategies for Crime Prevention

Crime has increased dramatically over the past 20 years, as have its expenses. The amount that countries spend on the police, prosecution, courts, and prisons is rising (Balogun, 2002). Legal experts' attention has gradually switched to creative methods of avoiding criminality rather than punishing it, as crime consistently resists so-called "punitive" efforts to fight it (Newman, 1979).

It has been demonstrated in numerous studies that crime prevention can dramatically reduce both expenses and offenses. For example, by employing closed-circuit television and civilian guards hired from the unemployed, criminality in public spaces can be reduced. Additionally, if young people from impoverished backgrounds receive job skills training or incentives to finish their education, they are less likely to be imprisoned (The Guardian, 14th April, 2000, Lagos).

Pinot Arlacchi, executive director of the United Nations Office for Drug Control and Crime Prevention, claims that there is a growing body of research demonstrating that crime prevention is beneficial and may be more cost-effective than conventional punitive tactics (ODCCP). "Those tactics are crucial for lowering traditional crime, but they can also shield children from organized crime recruiters," he observed.

The tenth United Nations Crime Congress on the Prevention of Crime and the Treatment of Offenders in Vienna, April 2000, will place a major priority on crime prevention techniques. The topic will also be covered in a workshop co-hosted by the International Centre for the Prevention of Crime (ICPC), a non-governmental organization with ties to the United Nations with offices in Montreal, Canada. The ICPC was established by a number of countries to compile data and best practices for international crime prevention. Congressmen focus on two key crime-prevention strategies that have been researched over the last 20 years. Consider social and situational prevention.

(a) Social Preventive Measures (Curbing Criminal Desire)

Social prevention attempts to address issues including poor parenting, inadequate early education, and poor physical and mental health that could influence a young person to commit crime. The community helps out by providing instruction, setting up facilities for young people without jobs, or offering free drug addiction treatment, and the approach has had amazing results (UN ICPC, 2000). Quantum Opportunities paid underprivileged teenagers for after-school activities such as peer tutoring, homework help, and community duties over a four-year period (1989–1993) in five American cities. According to the ICPC, the result was a 71% decrease in arrests. For every dollar invested in the program, savings on social welfare and other government-funded programs, such as adolescent counselling or employment insurance, amounted to around \$3.68.

Children from low-income housing who were disadvantaged were given access to competitive games during a two-year initiative in Ottawa, Canada, from 1980 to 1982. For every dollar spent on the initiative, the project returned around \$2.14 in economic benefits and a 50% reduction in delinquency.

In order to reduce crime, partnerships with local government, the police, or businesses have also been quite effective (Shelley, 1981). In Sydney, Australia, police teamed up with motorists, automakers, insurance providers, repair facilities, and local government to implement a wide range of public education and opportunity-based preventive measures, like more secure parking places. The program reduced auto theft by 25% in one year (Shelley, 1981).

(b) Situational crime prevention techniques (Reducing the Temptation of Criminality)

Modern technology, monitoring, and building design are used in situational crime prevention to deter potential criminals. As a result, there has been a dramatic increase in the private security and policing sectors, increased local citizen and non-police professional surveillance, and widespread use of technological tools and speed cameras (Skogan, 2000). Several government-funded situational projects have tried to change urban planning and architectural design to stop break-ins and burglaries, such as bank robberies (Skogan, 2000).

According to Swimmer (1999), the method is now a component of the official crime control policies in various European nations, including Britain, the Netherlands, and France, according to Swimmer (1999), who claims that it has been extremely effective in preventing a wide variety of offenses.

Universities, social workers, police, and city authorities collaborated on a project in Britain that started in 1986 to address the issue of repeat victimization on the Kirkholt housing estate in Rockdale. Project staff set up a neighbourhood watch program to monitor homes that had been targeted and to persuade locals to install better locks and bolts and remove coin-operated electric and gas meters (to reduce readily available cash). The Kirkholt programs showed a 95% decrease in burglaries by the end of the third year. The reduced amount of property/cash stolen covered the expenses of the program, and lower gas/electricity theft offset meter losses. For every dollar spent on police time, jail time, probation fees, and detention charges, it also saved around \$3.84. Kirkholt and other effective crime prevention initiatives persuaded the British government to adopt the Crime and Disorder Acts in 1998, which united local governments and police with other organizations like social services, education, probation, child protection, and the courts in developing community safety strategies (Swimmer, 1999). A three-year program aimed at policing, youth and family issues, domestic abuse and burglary, and other concerns received funding from the government totalling roughly \$450 million. According to ICPC Director Irwin Waller, the industrialized nations are spending gradually on what is effective. But he said that the ignited budgets made it impossible to spend the same amount in poor countries (like Nigeria) where crime prevention and control are desperately needed.

The United Nations Development Fund for Women (UNDFW) has pioneered a number of initiatives aimed at increasing public and governmental awareness of the risks associated with the trafficking of women and girls for sex. According to UNDFW Executive Director Noleen Heyzer, we must eliminate the secrecy and taboos surrounding this issue in order to increase awareness and stop the trafficking of women and girls. One thing that was done was to talk about the dangers of human trafficking with the girls and staff of Russian orphanages that were far away.

Orphanages encourage employers to look for new employees among the girls who must leave the facility by the age of 17, but many of these "employers," in Ms. Heyzer's opinion, are connected to international traffickers. The effort has already produced fruitful outcomes: "Orphanages and screening recruiters are now aware of the potential for trafficking, and the girls themselves." She spoke.

A fictional film depicting the entire trafficking network from Nepal to the brothels of Bombay was developed as part of another UNDFW project using case studies of Nepalese women and girls who had been misled into prostitution. The movie, which recently had its world premiere in New Delhi, India, will be screened in Nepalese communities and at important events all around South Asia.

Even though several projects have demonstrated that crime prevention is effective, there are still obstacles. There are now ethnic disputes. One criticism of situational prevention is that it can create a "fortress society" of mistrustful people who barricade themselves inside their homes. Businesses have raised concerns about the expense of such initiatives. Because paying all claims with the smallest number of controls saves retail shops money, they frequently reject suggestions for how to reduce stealing (Balogun, 2002).

6. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Social conflict theory and functionalist theory are the two theories used in this paper.

Theory of Social Conflict

The proletariat and the bourgeoisie are two examples of social groups with different amounts of material and non-material resources, according to the Marxist theory of social conflict, which also contends that the more powerful groups use their influence to oppress the weaker ones. The two ways this exploitation is carried out are through brute force, which is typically

used by the police, the army, and the economy (Dahrendorf, 1959). Money, according to earlier social conflict theorists, is the mechanism that causes social disorder. Conflict theory is linked to left-leaning political activism and radical orientation. The class struggle between the owners of the means of production and the workers is how Karl Marx conceptualizes contemporary society, or capitalist society. This conflict, which can go through different stages depending on how aware and organized the working class is, ends with a showdown between the two sides and the end of the bourgeoisie. Marxist theory holds that after the bourgeoisie is overthrown, the workers will erect a socialist society where all conflicts will be resolved.

According to the theory, the relationship is unequal and favours the owner. The conflict theorist will use this kind of relationship to demonstrate how social relationships are all about exploitation and power. According to Marxism, this conflict—which is the result of the powerful and wealthy exploiting the weak and poor—has dominated human history. The social conflict theory asserts that because the various institutions of society, such as the legal and political systems, are tools of ruling class dominance and serve to further its interests, groups within a capitalist society tend to interact in a destructive manner that allows neither mutual benefit nor much cooperation. Dahrendorf (1959) suggests a workers' revolution as a remedy for this issue in order to end the capitalist class's hegemony over politics and the economy and to restructure society around the principles of collective ownership and mass democratic control (Dahrendorf, 1959).

The strength of social conflict theory in this paper is based on the idea that the social, political, and economic forces operating within a society, including competition over limited resources, private wealth accumulation, achievement, and exploitation, among others, are the fundamental causes of the barriers to effective policing in Nigeria. Social disorder is unavoidable because people have different ideas and interests, which are often at odds with one another.

Theory of Functionalism

In sociology, the functionalist explanation of society has a complicated and lengthy history. Auguste Comte (1798–1857) and Herbert Spencer (1820–1903) both heavily influenced it. It was created by Talcott Parsons and improved by Emile Durkheim (1858–1917). But Alfred Reginald Radcliffe-Brown, who, along with Bronislaw Malinowski, might be considered the founders of modern functionalism, presented the most conclusive claim concerning functionalism. According to Radcliff-Brown (1959:181), "a particular social usage's function is the contribution it makes to the functioning of the overall system." This contribution could be constructive or destructive. The input is considered to be functional whenever it is constructive. For example, Durkheim believed that religion benefits society by encouraging social cohesion. Durkheim provided a comprehensive analysis of society. According to him, society is made up of many pieces, none of which are greater than the whole, making society "sui-generis" (all-in-all). He chose sui-generis simply to emphasize the value of the community as a whole over the contributions of its individual members. As a result, the ability of the pieces to survive is determined by how well they function. When different parts of society don't do what they're supposed to do, society is in an abnormal state.

Therefore, institutions that positively contribute to the survival and efficient operation of society are said to be functioning. As a corollary, there are additional human actions that, by their negative effects, change the delicate equilibrium of the social system. The dysfunctional components of human society are what Robert Merton refers to as these. For instance, war can have a very negative impact on how well civilization is run.

Malinowski (1944) emphasized the significance of functionalism by stating that each established social pattern contributes in its own unique way to meeting the requirements for the proper operation of the wider society. This is usually referred to as "the postulate of universal functionalism" in sociological literature. Goode (1951) disagreed with this idea by saying that some social interactions have nothing to do with how well society works as a whole.

Through his AGIL pattern variable, Talcott Parsons analyzes this. Where L-Latent pattern maintenance, G-Goal attainment, A-Adaptation, and I-Integration.

The role of adaptation is to distribute scarce resources, and economic institutions carry out this function. To achieve a goal, one must mobilize the resources and energy required for the social objective and the political institution's survival. The legal institutions carry out integration, which focuses on the coordination of all other institutions to maintain peace. The family, educational, and religious institutions perform latent pattern maintenance, which gives the means for preserving the traits of a society. The four institutions, in Parsons' view, are necessary for maintaining social balance.

The effectiveness of the functionalist model in this study rests on its ability to highlight the role that law enforcement plays in upholding social order and the rule of law, as well as how the failure of the security sector can result in social unrest and societal instability.

7. DISCUSSION

This paper examined the obstacles to effective policing in Nigeria. It revealed factors such as mass unemployment, poverty, declining income, and political intolerance, among others, as factors responsible for the seeming high crime incidence in Nigeria. However, in response to the seeming high rate of crime in Nigeria, the police have designed strategies such as surveillance, intelligence gathering, money escort, undercover work, stop and search and detain, investigation, among others, to curtail crime and criminal behaviour. These strategies were, however, revealed not to be highly effective and this was attributed to the myriad of challenges facing the Nigerian security architecture, among which are uncooperative attitudes of members of the public, inadequate crime prevention and control equipment, poor remuneration, corruption, inadequate manpower, inadequate funding, among a myriad of others. Based on the literature reviewed in this paper, one can therefore posit that Nigerian police have not been able to respond adequately to the seeming escalating crime wave despite the good strategies designed to curtail crime and criminality as well as create a safer and more secure environment for socio-economic development in the country.

8. CONCLUSION

Given the recent spate of violence and the level of degeneration in the body polity, it is reasonable to conclude that the Nigerian police have demonstrated glaring deficiencies and an inability to effectively enforce the law and maintain social order. It is no longer safe to walk alone during the day for a variety of reasons, including robberies, assassinations, arson, public treasury looting, forcible rape, aggravated assault, Boko Haram insurgency, kidnapping, abduction, gangsterism, gunmen/herdsmen, and suicide bombing, among others.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on what has been said so far, the following suggestions were made to improve Nigeria's police strategies and their ability to stop and prevent crime:

The government should focus its efforts on addressing the root causes of crime, i.e., correcting the conditions that make crime a viable alternative to law-abiding behaviour should also ensure jobs are made available for the teeming population of school leavers of all categories to forestall the probability of some of these joining criminal gangs since unemployment was found to be one of the factors responsible for the seeming high rate of crime.

Because criminal activity was discovered to be a dynamic and ever-changing, complex process, police management should train and re-train officers to deal with new and sophisticated methods of crime and criminal behaviour.

The government should provide the police with adequate crime prevention and control weapons as well as necessary logistics and functional communication gadgets that will make information dissemination on the activities of criminals quick.

Police need better pay and should therefore be well remunerated and also provided with decent accommodation to enhance their performance. Similarly, police management should remind citizens of the importance of always cooperating and working with the police in terms of providing adequate and timely information on the activities of suspected and even suspicious people in their neighbourhood.

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